

Waste management and larval source reduction

Co-creation workshop summary

KIVUNGE Hospital

The following challenges were explored in the workshops:

Physical workshop

How the current management of **medical** and **non-medical waste** can lead to discarded items that become breeding sites.

Online survey

Informal dumping sites that become mosquito breeding sites

Unmanaged garden areas hiding potential breeding sites like discarded waste

management of **medical** and **non-medical waste**

Underlying Causes:

- Some patients and relatives dispose wastes on the ground
- Mixing of wastes causing wastes to be left by the cars
- Shortage of waste bins and bags
- Lack of special carrier to support moving wastes from the wards to the waste collection area
- Delays in collecting/removing wastes
Bursting of waste bags during the process of picking and sending wastes to the storage area
- Waste bags not tied properly
- Leaving doors open at the waste storage area
- Wastes being collected by open car

Informal dumping sites

Underlying Causes:

- The gardeners made that area to dispose of cut grasses, then people start to dump other waste
- Lack of education on environmental protection
- People finds it difficult to go to the designated waste storage area and just throws the waste anywhere
- Before having this waste collection zone, people used to put waste there and now it is a habit
- Lack of understanding, especially patients
- Lack of bins nearby that area, also the hospital not having good strategies on proper waste management
- Shortage of waste bins

Unmanaged garden areas

Underlying Causes:

- Gardeners are not well supervised to plan their activities well
- Shortage of gardeners, Kivunge hospital is a hospital with a large area therefore the shortage of gardeners leads to activities not going well
- Shortage of equipment for cutting grass (machines, fuel and other garden tools)
- Places of the building that are not used ; those places not being attended hence creating bushes

Summary of the proposed solutions

BLUE - Who is responsible

Management Suggestions:

These suggestions will be shared with the hospital management through meeting. The hospital management will decide whether they can support and implement them.

1. Create a timetable for waste and garden management and supervise it

- a. Management to create a schedule for collecting waste from wards and outdoor litter bins regularly so they do not become overfilled. - **Hospital management, cleaners**
- b. Include grass cutting in the schedule, so it is maintained at a height that does not hide discarded objects - **Hospital management, gardeners**
- c. Include schedule for waste collection by municipal and medical waste collection company truck from the designated waste storage area. - **Hospital management, municipal and waste collection companies**
- d. Management to supervise that all responsible parties have carried out their part of the timetable. - **Hospital management,**
- e. Put up the schedule in a public place, so all staff can see it and help ensure that it is maintained. - **Hospital management + all hospital staff**

2. Ensure adequate materials, tools and resources

- a. provide more bags of all colours for all types of waste - **Hospital management, cleaning company (Slim)**
- b. supply gloves for carrying waste for cleaning staff - **Hospital management, cleaning company (Slim)**
- c. Provide fuel for grass cutting equipment - **Hospital management**
- d. More grass cutting equipment - **Hospital management**
- e. Provide a carrier for cleaners to safely transport waste from the wards to the designated waste storage area - **Hospital management**
- f. Employ more gardeners if possible due to the large size of the hospital sites - **Hospital management**

3. Education and training (supported by posters)

- a. Management to ensure bags are not overfull or exceed weight - **Hospital management, cleaners**
- b. Ensure sharp objects are disposed of properly - **cleaners**
- c. Cleaning staff to ensure waste bags are tied - **cleaners**
- d. Education on the importance of maintaining the garden spaces and regular grass cutting - **Hospital management, gardeners**
- e. Cleaning supervisor to ensure that door is closed - **cleaners**
- f. Encourage that every hospital worker has the right to observe if the bushes have become overgrown, to reduce them, and to eliminate them completely, especially in the area surrounding them. - **Hospital management + all hospital staff**

4. Create a waste bag label system

- a. Create a labeling system to show which type of waste is in which bag in case the proper coloured bag cannot be used due to lack of waste bags. (**Cleaners, hospital management, municipal and waste collection companies**)
 - i. Labeling system to be decided by cleaners so it is simple to implement, uses available resources and is easy to understand
 - ii. Inform the municipal and any other waste collectors of the labeling system to avoid waste being left at the hospital.

5. Hospital clean up day

- a. Hospital users could periodically participate in a communal cleaning of the outdoor surroundings and gardens. - **all hospital staff, Hospital management to organise**

6. Designated garden waste area

- a. Find a designated area away from commonly used areas of the hospital for cut grasses and other plant matter - **Hospital management, gardeners**
- b. Have a sign saying that this is only for grasses or other plant materials (MBD-Free to provide)
- c. Gardeners to make sure to also check this area for inorganic discarded waste and dispose of properly. - **gardeners**

Summary of the proposed solutions implemented by MBD-Free Project

If co-creators agree, these suggestions would be further developed together with feedback from the Kivunge co-creators.

1. Provide educational posters promoting good waste management practices in following areas:

- a. By the ward bins. Aims of the poster are:
 - i. Remind staff to use the correct bags or label them
 - ii. To not overload the bins and waste bags
 - iii. Inform the cleaning team if the bins are becoming full
 - iv. Ensure sharp objects are disposed of properly in designated sharp bins
 - v. How this helps prevent MBD transmission

- b. Waste storage area. Aims of the poster are:
 - i. Put a sign on the door of the waste storage area to keep door closed
 - ii. Ensure waste bags are tied properly
 - iii. How this helps prevent MBD transmission

- c. Garden areas
 - i. Reminder to discard of waste in bins
 - ii. Education on the importance of maintaining the garden spaces
 - iii. How this helps prevent MBD transmission

- d. In common dumping areas
 - i. sign that prohibits dumping waste in unofficial areas
 - ii. How this helps prevent MBD transmission

- e. Designated garden waste area (if inacted by management)
 - i. sign for designated garden waste area saying that this is only for grasses or other plant materials
 - ii. How this helps prevent MBD transmission

2. Design and installation of more outdoor litter bins based on feedback requirements:

- a. Design the bins so they do not need to be touched to discard waste, e.g. pedal operated or with opening to throw in waste
- b. Use strong material and robust design
- c. Improve the stability of the bins so they cannot easily be knocked over by animals.
- d. Consider a design that does not require a waste bag in it due to the shortage of these.